

CHEMISTRY

INFLUENCE OF SUBMICRON CARBON OBTAINED BY PLASMOCHEMICAL DESTRUCTION OF ORGANICS-CONTAINING WASTEWATER ON THE PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE WATER-COAL FUEL

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Abstract

The study investigated the potential to improve the rheological properties of water-carbon composite fuel (CWCF) by incorporating microdispersed carbon (MC) produced by plasmochemical degradation of organ-containing wastewater. The research employed coal of P and DG grades to simulate actual CWCF. Coal grade P is semi-anthracite, while grade DG corresponds to highly volatile bituminous coal. The results showed that the addition of MC improved the sedimentation stability of the CWCF from 1-2 to 8-10 days. Adding MC to CWCF improves its rheological stability and reduces its sensitivity to mechanical stress.

Keywords: composite water-coal fuel, plasmochemical destruction, microdispersed carbon, sedimentation, rheology.

Introduction.

Plasma-chemical degradation is a highly effective method for treating wastewater containing harmful and toxic organic compounds. This technology offers several advantages over traditional treatment methods [1]. It is universal for all organic contaminants, does not require the use of materials or reagents, and can be used to build closed, non-waste water management systems.

Plasma-chemical destruction has high energy intensity, so it is recommended to combine it with energy-generating technologies. This process produces a significant amount of finely dispersed carbon material in the liquid phase, which can serve as combustion catalysts and stabilizers for suspension fuels due to their branched active surface of submicron size.

Composite water-coal fuel (CWCF) is a promising type of suspension fuel [2]. Although CWCF has environmental advantages over coal, its lower calorific value due to the presence of water in its composition is a disadvantage. However, this can be eliminated by using organically-containing wastewater as a dispersion medium for CWCF [3], resulting in a more caloric fuel. Liquid organic wastes that can be used as a dispersion medium for fuel dispersion systems vary in composition, viscosity, density, and intermolecular bonds. When filling such media with fine coal particles, the problem of their uniform distribution in the volume of the dispersed system arises. When coal particles are in water or alcohol, they interact with the dispersion medium through hydrogen bonds. However, when using media that contain hydrocarbons and aromatic compounds, hydrophobic interactions occur. Another challenge in preparing organic-mineral dispersed systems is selecting appropriate reagents for plasticization and stabilization. Many reagents that work well for water-coal fuels are not suitable for organo-mineral fuels.

To use CWCF as fuel for industrial and domestic power plants, it must meet specific operational requirements. Chemical additives are necessary to ensure stability, viscosity, and fluidity. Commonly used additives in CWCF formulations include lignosulfonates Na, Ca,

Mg, sulfonated naphthalene, and melamine derivatives [3, 4]. However, these stabilizers are sensitive to changes in pH, ionic composition, and coal type. Additionally, the use of liquid waste containing organic substances as part of the CWCF can alter the spatial colloidal structures formed by the addition of plasticizers, stabilizers, and dispersants. Certain components of wastewater, such as cationic surfactants, polyelectrolytes, and humic substances, can cause deactivation.

To use fuel oil as a power source for industrial and domestic power plants, it must meet specific operational requirements. Chemical additives are necessary to achieve the desired stability, viscosity, and fluidity. Commonly used additives in CFC formulations include lignosulfonates Na, Ca, Mg, sulfonated naphthalene, and melamine derivatives [3, 4]. However, these stabilizers are sensitive to changes in pH, ionic composition, and coal type.

Additionally, the use of liquid waste containing organic substances as part of the CWCF alters the spatial colloidal structures formed by the addition of plasticizers, stabilizers, and dispersants. Certain components of wastewater, such as cationic surfactants, polyelectrolytes, and humic substances, can deactivate the stabilizers' effect [5].

The surface of coal particles can be modified by adsorbed organic molecules, which can alter their properties and electrokinetic potential. This, in turn, affects the rheological behavior of composite dispersions [3]. To stabilize CWCF, highly dispersed carbon can be introduced into its composition to enhance the formation of stable spatial structures. The use of bimodal coal grinding allows for the production of CWCF with maximum solid phase content, which would be impossible otherwise. This process involves the use of both coarse particles (>100 μm) and fine particles (<50 μm). In the composition of CWCF (pre-plasma-chemically treated organics-containing wastewater), carbon particles formed by the conversion of organic contaminants in a plasma flame can provide stabilization and bimodal distribution [3]. Due to the catalytic properties of CF, it

is also possible to increase the degree of burnout and calorific value of the fuel [6, 7].

The study aims to investigate the effect of plasma-chemical treatment of organ-containing wastewater and micro-dispersed carbon additives on the rheological parameters of the hard coal-based CF based on P and DG grades.

Experimental part

To simulate real CWCF, we used coal of grade "P", Ad = 10.7%, and grade "DG", Ad = 15.4%, as a

dispersion medium - water, after plasma chemical treatment. Coal P is a semi-anthracite, and grade DG corresponds to highly volatile bituminous coal. The sample obtained by plasma-chemical destruction of organ-containing wastewater was used as microdispersed carbon.

Table 1 shows the technical and elemental composition of the coal and microdispersed carbon used in this study.

Table 1.

Technical and elemental analysis of coal and microdispersed carbon (MC)

Coal grade	Technical analysis, %			Elemental analysis, % <i>daf</i>				
	humidity	ash content	volatile substances	C	H	N	O	S
MC	5.6	7.2	0.35	96.8	0.8	0.2	2.1	0.1
DG	9.3	22.3	43.8	76.2	4.9	1.1	13.7	4.1
P	5.1	25.0	14.9	88.5	3.8	0.67	5.33	1.7

The grinding of the initial coal of 1- 5 mm fraction was carried out with ceramic balls in a porcelain drum with a capacity of 2 dm³ in a roller mill. The particle size distribution of the suspensions was determined using a set of sieves SLM-200. In order to exclude the influence of the particle size distribution on the rheological behavior of the suspensions, the coal powders

had an identical particle size distribution: 250-160 μm - 28%, 160-100 μm - 24%, 100-63 μm - 12%, 63-40 μm - 32%, <40 μm - 9%. The MC sample had the following particle size distribution: 100-40 μm - 18%, 40-10 μm - 24%, <10 μm - 58%.

Table 2.

Structural and sorption characteristics of coal and microdispersed carbon obtained by DFT from the analysis of N₂ adsorption: specific gravity (ρ), specific surface area (S_{sp}), pore volume (V_{pore}), and pore diameter (d_{pore})

Coal grade	ρ , g/sm ³	S_{sp} , M ² /g	V_{pore} , sm ³ /g	d_{pore} , nm
MC	1.10	81.68	0.064	22.61
DG	1.32	1.39	0.053	7.67
P	1.51	4.72	0.019	7.88

Table 3

Chemical additives used as stabilizers, dispersants and plasticizers of CWCF

Sulfonaphthaleneformaldehyde (SNF) (OOO "Pigment-Dniepr", DSTU 6848-79)	
Sulfomelamine formaldehyde (SMF) Melment F 10 BASF	
Polycarboxylate (PK) Melflux F 1610 BASF	

The reagents were used without preliminary preparation.

The effective viscosity η and flow curves of the samples were measured on a Rheotest-2 device at $t=20^\circ\text{C}$. The range of measurement of shear rates D was limited to values from 1 to 437 s^{-1} .

The sedimentation stability (St) was studied by the time of delamination of the CWCF sample in a measuring cylinder.

Results and discussion

Table 4 shows the data on the sedimentation stability of the CWCF based on different types of coal in the presence of different dispersants at 60% of the dispersed phase concentration. The MC content varied from 0.1 to 2%. Suspensions of pure P and DG coals with a solid phase content of $> 40\%$ without the introduction of dispersants and plasticizers are much thickened and therefore were not studied for comparison.

Sedimentation resistance of CWCF to delamination with different MC content at 20°C .

Table 4.

Sedimentation resistance of CWCF with the addition of microdispersed carbon (MC)

Composition	C MC, %					
	0,1	0,25	0,5	1	1,5	2
	Time to delamination, days					
60%P+1% PK	2	4	6	10	10	10
60%DG+1% PK	2	4	8	10	10	10
60% P +1% SMF	2	2.5	6	8	10	10
60% DG +1% SMF	4	6	6	8	10	10
60% P +1% SNF	2	5	7	10	10	10
60% DG +1% SNF	2	6	8	8	10	10

The above results show that the introduction of submicron carbon in amounts $> 1\%$ ensures the sedimentation stability of the CWCF for 10 days. Further increase of the MC content does not lead to a proportional increase in sedimentation stability and is therefore impractical.

All the reagent additives studied show approximately the same efficiency, so in further experiments,

the SNF additive was used as the cheapest and most accessible.

Tables 5 and 6 show the results of the influence of MC on the rheological properties of the CWCF based on P and DG coals.

Table 5.

Effect of MC on the rheological properties and stability of the CWCF based on P coal (1% SNF additive).

Dispersed phase	Concentration of coal φ , %	η , Pa·s at $D_r=9c^{-1}$	St, days
Coal P	50	0.70	0.25
	60	1.34	0.5
	70	1.85	2
Coal P +0.5% MC	50	0.98	3
	60	1.58	3
	70	2.01	4
Coal P +1.5% MC	50	2.74	5
	60	5.12	5
	70	9.70	6
Coal P +3% MC	50	3.41	5
	60	10.05	6
	70	18.60	6

Table 6

Effect of MC on the rheological properties and stability of CWCF based on DG coal (1% SNF additive).

Dispersed phase	φ , %	η , Pa·s at $D_r=9c^{-1}$	St, days
Coal DG	50	0.74	2
	60	1.29	2
	70	1.77	2
Coal DG +0.5% MC	50	0.96	4
	60	1.41	8
	70	1.87	8
Coal DG +1.5% MC	50	2.23	6
	60	4.65	8
	70	9.07	8
Coal DG +3% MC	50	2.88	6
	60	8.45	10
	70	14.4	8

For P and DG coals, it can be noted that the use of MC additives also leads to an increase in sedimentation resistance and thickening. Moreover, the effect on P-grade coal is more noticeable than for DG and anthracite. Compared to DG, the surface of anthracite and lean coal is more hydrophobic. Therefore, it is more energetically advantageous for hydrophobic MC to bind to hydrophobic surfaces. The lower values of sedimentation resistance and viscosity for semi-anthracite compared to lean coal are associated with a more ordered surface of semi-anthracite with fewer active centers.

Summarizing the above data, it can be concluded that the effectiveness of MC additives for modifying the properties of CWCF s based on coals of different grades is evident. However, since such systems are prone to thickening at a high concentration of the solid phase ($>60\%$), it is necessary to investigate the effect of surfactants to increase the fluidity of suspensions.

Based on the data obtained, it can be concluded that carbon micro- and nanoparticle admixtures with increased dispersion demonstrate the ability to form coagulation structures even when they are contained in suspensions in the amount of several percent. Further adjustment of the properties of the CWCF is possible only through a detailed study of the surface phenomena and colloidal and chemical features of the formation of double electric layers of particles of the dispersed phase.

The fluidity curves of the CWCF with additives of 2% MC and 1% SNF are illustrated in Fig. 1. It is noticeable that all the studied flow curves of the CWCF modified with submicron carbon have a significant deflection in the D_r region: $0-150 c^{-1}$, indicating that these systems have a pseudoplastic flow character. The deflection on these curves indicates the formation of a structured system, and the greater the deflection, the greater the stress required to destroy such a structure. Systems based on P-grade coal are less stable than those

based on DG coal. This is due to the higher number of active groups on the surface of DG coal, which provides higher structural strength. In Fig. 4, the viscosity of all CWCFs decreases with increasing shear stress. For all the studied samples, when D reaches 150–200 c^{-1} , the structure of the suspension is destroyed and at $D > 200 \text{ c}^{-1}$ it acquires a Newtonian yield character.

As can be seen from the data (Fig. 1), the rheological curves of the studied CFRPs are satisfactorily described by the Oswald de Ville equation:

$$\tau = KD^n$$

Where: τ is the shear stress; K is the coefficient of structure; D is the shear rate; n is the flow index ($n < 1$ for pseudoplastic structures).

For the curves with P and DG coals, $n = 0.50$ and 0.63 , respectively, and when MK is added, $n = 0.52$ and 0.67 , which characterizes these CWCFs as pseudoplastic.

Most pseudoplastic structures are characterized by a loss of structure under the influence of high shear rates and the restoration of the initial high viscosity when high loads are removed and at rest. This phenomenon of thixotropy is characterized by hysteresis of the flow curves and is typical for the CWCF, the dispersed phase of which is coal particles. Fig. 1 shows the flow curves with a gradual increase and subsequent decrease in shear rate for the CWCF based on P and DG coals without and in the presence of MC additives.

Fig. 1 Flow curves of the CWCF ($St=60\%$) with 2% MC and 1% SNF additives (continuous curve - D rising; dashed curve - D falling).

As can be seen from the flow curves with decreasing D , the structure of the CWCF in the presence of submicron carbon is restored at higher D (100–50 s^{-1}) than for structures without MC (50–25 s^{-1}). Faster restoration of the structure is facilitated by the branched surface of the MC and its greater reactivity in interparticle interactions.

From a practical point of view, this means that CWCFs with submicron carbon additives are less sensitive to mechanical stress than systems with coal. It takes much less time to restore their damaged structure. This can be an advantage when transporting and storing CWCF.

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